

1 **GREB1 mediates resistance in hormone receptor positive breast cancer.**

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6 Between 10-20% of women with hormone receptor positive (HR+) breast cancer will experience
7 disease recurrence, also known as relapse, following treatment with endocrine therapy (ET) that blocks
8 the function of the sex hormone estrogen. Relapse is associated with spread of disease to the brain, also
9 or central nervous system metastasis. We conducted an expression screen using over a dozen culture
10 systems and tumor models to discover genes responsible for conferring resistance to endocrine therapies
11 in women with hormone receptor positive breast cancer, including luminal A and luminal molecular
12 subtypes. We identified *GREB1* as a leading candidate molecule with putative resistance properties *in*
13 *vivo*. *GREB1* expression was induced in hyperplastic settings, indicating its function was associated with
14 transformation in solid tissues. *GREB1* expression was hormone (estrogen) responsive, and its
15 expression was enriched in the breast. While *GREB1* expression was modestly affected by
16 estrogen-blocking endocrine therapy with the selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM) tamoxifen, its
17 expression was virtually eliminated with the aromatase inhibitor (AI) letrozole. Reduction of *GREB1*
18 expression was strongly correlated with pathological complete response in humans *in vivo*. Thus, we
19 have concluded from weight of scientific evidence that treatment with the aromatase inhibitor letrozole, as
20 compared to the SERM agent tamoxifen, is likely to confer superior CNS outcomes and provide enhanced
21 control of disease in humans with HR+ luminal A and luminal B breast cancer. We have identified a gene
22 associated with and likely in part responsible for disease resistance in humans with hormone receptor
23 positive breast cancer.
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1 **Results**

2 We isolated GREB1 in an expression screen for genes functioning in resistance to endocrine
 3 therapy (including both tamoxifen and fulvestrant) using multiple estrogen receptor-positive (ER+) human
 4 cell lines and xenograft models. In multiple *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of resistance to tamoxifen, GREB1
 5 was among the genes, across the entire transcriptome, whose expression changed most significantly
 6 transcriptome-wide.

7 We first studied GREB1 tissue expression and estrogen responsiveness.

8 **Figure 1: GREB1 displays highest tissue expression in the breast.**

9 GREB1 was expressed in the mammary gland (breast),
 10 uterus, ovaries and prostate, with lower expression in
 11 other tissues including the brain.

12 We measured total transcription in hormone
 13 positive MCF7 breast cancer cells in the presence and
 14 absence of ESR1 depletion to understand how changes
 15 in estrogen signaling affected GREB1 expression.

16 **Profile** GDS4061 / 205862_at
 17 **Title** Estrogen receptor alpha-silenced MCF7 breast cancer cells
 18 **Organism** Homo sapiens

19 **Figure 2: GREB1 expression is controlled by the**
 20 **sex hormone estrogen and the estrogen receptor.**

21 GSE27473
 22 *n*=3 MCF7 breast cancer cells (human)
 23 *n*=3 MCF7 with ESR1 depletion (siRNA)

24 GREB1 expression was fully estrogen responsive in human breast cancer cells *in vitro* (Figure 2A).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205862_at	1.90e-13	52.6848889	21.583374	4.97815667	GREB1	389/54675	99.3

25 We measured total transcription following 24 hours of *in vitro* exposure to estradiol (E2). GREB1
 26 was the 23rd most differentially expressed gene transcriptome-wide in response to treatment with
 27 estrogen hormone (Figure 2B)

GSE37386

n=3 MCF7 (HR+, siNT, control)

n=4 MCF7 breast cancer cells treated with estrogen *in vitro* (HR+, siNR, 24 hours E2)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1721170	6.13e-14	-1.76e+01	21.72367	-2.35	GREB1	23/47230	99.95

Like estrogen and the estrogen receptor, glucocorticoids mediate therapeutic and biologic function through binding of a ligand to a hormone receptor which translocates to the nucleus for direct transcriptional activation with co-factors and other nuclear machinery. We studied total transcription in the mouse liver following administration of glucocorticoids (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: GREB1 is responsive to a glucocorticoid.

Profile GDS5036 / 38271

Title Glucocorticoid effect on the female liver

Organism *Mus musculus*

GSE24256

n=3 female liver, PBS (11 weeks of age)

n=3 female liver, dexamethasone (1mg/kg; i.p. 6hrs)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
38271	1.16e-06	-1.30e+01	5.801474	-4.22610186	Greb1	22/45018	99.95

GREB1 was transcriptionally activated in response to *in vivo* glucocorticoid administration in the murine liver (Figure 3). Since we identified GREB1 as a resistance gene product, we measured total transcription during transformation of the mammary gland, in normal terminal ducts and hyperplastic ducts to understand if and how GREB1 was associated with transformation (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: GREB1 expression is activated in hyperplasia.

GSE7377

n=8 normal terminal ducts

n=8 hyperplastic terminal ducts

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
G7662187_3p_at	7.83e-04	-3.97151267	-0.47329	-2.11402174	GREB1	204/61359	99.67

GREB1 was strongly activated in the hyperplastic duct of the mammary gland (Figure 4), indicating GREB1 possessed, separate from its role in the estrogen-rich breast, a separate, related function during transformation of the breast (Figure 4).

Breast cancers are defined by PAM50 molecular subtype classification as basal-like or luminal subtype, expressing hormone receptor or not, respectively. We compared expression of GREB1 at clinical presentation in basal subtype and hormone positive luminal subtype breast cancers in humans (Figure 5).

Figure 5: GREB1 expression is high in luminal subtype breast cancers in humans and is a defining transcriptional characteristic of the luminal subtype.

GSE1561

n=16 basal subtype breast cancer (primary tumors)

n=30 luminal subtype breast cancer (primary tumors)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205862_at	9.08e-08	-6.34	7.755848	-2.39	GREB1	313/22215	98.6

GREB1 expression, at clinical presentation, notwithstanding changes in expression during resistance to endocrine therapy or other cancer therapies, was consistent with a function for GREB1 in hormone receptor positive cancer, associated with the luminal subtype (Figure 5).

We identified GREB1 in an expression screen for mediators of resistance to endocrine therapy, which in breast cancer include tamoxifen and letrozole which effect hormone deprivation through distinct mechanisms. Aromatase inhibitors like letrozole inhibit conversion of androgens to estrogen, while selective estrogen receptor modulators act as antagonists at the nuclear receptor ESR1. This raised the possibility that endocrine therapy agents will be associated with clinically distinct therapeutic responses associated with or directly attributable to changes in GREB1 expression, following treatment with an endocrine therapy (Figure 6 and Figure 7), as well as resistance occurring in a significant fraction of hormone receptor positive patients. Thus, GREB1 was endogenously enriched in the breast, its expression was induced during hyperplastic transformation, its expression was significantly enriched in hormone positive cancers, and we identified the GREB1 gene products as a top mediator of resistance in humans with hormone receptor positive breast cancer (luminal A and luminal B molecular subtypes).

Figure 6: GREB1 is the single most differentially expressed gene transcriptome-wide in pre- and post-treatment biopsies in response to treatment with the endocrine therapy agent letrozole, an aromatase inhibitor.

n=18 tumors (breast; human) pre-treatment with letrozole
n=17 tumors (breast; human) post-treatment with letrozole

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205862_at	1.08e-08	7.3409942	9.52033	2.46	GREB1	1/54675	99.998

Following treatment with letrozole (femtara), GREB1 expression was almost completely reduced. GREB1 reduction was the most significant gene expression change in the tumor transcriptome of humans with breast cancer following treatment with letrozole (**Figure 6**).

We next measured total transcription in a cohort of patients treated with a separate endocrine therapy agent, tamoxifen, to understand how GREB1 expression responded to treatment with a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM) in humans (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7: GREB1 transcriptional response in patients following treatment with tamoxifen is weak.

GSE147271
n=62 tumors (breast; human) pre-treatment with tamoxifen
n=40 tumors (breast; human) post-treatment with tamoxifen

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P412476	7.31e-05	4.12471	1.14022	0.6031531	GREB1	11405/31300	63.6

Finally, we studied total transcription associated with pathologic complete response (pCR) in human breast cancer, in a mixed cohort of women with breast cancer treated with paclitaxel and radiation. Though implicit, and a treatment outcome rather than a chronologically separated recurrence event (resistance) we explicitly interpret partial response (pPR), as well as residual disease (RD) as failure to induce remission and/or resistance (treatment failure).

Figure 8: Reduction in GREB1 is strongly associated with pathologic complete response (pCR) in human breast cancer following taxane treatment (see also, in reference, Figure 5).

GSE22513

$n=8$ pCR (pathologic complete response)

$n=20$ pPR (pathologic partial response)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205862_at	1.32e-03	-3.566677	-1.015175	-2.4620098	GREB1	1333/54675	97.6

GREB1 was among the top 2.5% of gene transcriptome-wide whose expression was most different when comparing total transcription in the primary tumors of breast cancer patients pathologic complete response (pCR) or partial response (pPR), indicating that separate from its role in mediating recurrence (resistance), GREB1 was a marker or indicator, likely reflective of its active biologic role in estrogen receptor signaling, and as a transcriptional correlate in reduction or suppression of the transformed state, as opposed to a simple marker of response.

Silencing of ESR1 in human cells resulted in reduction of GREB1. To validate a functional relationship between GREB1 and hormone receptor signaling by ESR1, we studied transcriptional co-regulation across tissues transcriptome-wide using SEEK. We identified ESR1 and PGR1 (progesterone receptor), in addition to the prolactin receptor as GREB1 co-regulated gene products (Figure 9).

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value
	GREB1	9687	-3.2000	0.0000

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Description	%Co-reg (/17862)
3	PGR	5241	1.7850	0.0000	progesterone receptor	99.98
4	PRLR	5618	1.7100	0.0001	prolactin receptor	99.98
5	ESR1	2099	1.6442	0.0000	estrogen receptor 1	99.97

We confirmed a functional role for GREB1 as a direct mediator of estrogen signaling, likely through a poorly described interaction with the estrogen receptor (ESR1) that we defined here at the transcriptional level, by depletion of GREB1 in human breast cancer cells. Genetic depletion of GREB1 resulted in silencing of ESR1, consistent with a function for GREB1 as a regulator of estrogen signaling or as a mediator of ESR1 function, reflected by silencing of ESR1 in response to GREB1 loss (Figure 10). A more modest but perceptible reduction in aromatase (*CYP19A1*) expression was observed in response to GREB1 depletion (Figure 10).

GSE37386

n=3 MCF7, siNT (non-targeting siRNA control)
n=4 MCF7, siGREB1 (GREB1 siRNA depletion)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1678535	1.70e-05	5.58	2.872718	6.10e-01	ESR1	527/47321	98.9
ILMN_1897864	2.74e-01	1.12	-6.254121	1.35e-01	CYP19A1	17719/47321	62.6

Discussion

Superior treatment response (specifically, recurrence at distant sites) in hormone-receptor positive patients treated with letrozole versus those treated with tamoxifen has been described (1). We demonstrated here selective control of GREB1 by letrozole, and argue this is likely to account at least in part for this disparity. GREB1 is estrogen-responsive, expressed in the breast, activated during transformation in the mammary gland, enriched in hormone receptor positive luminal subtype breast cancer at clinical presentation. Reduction in GREB1 expression is strongly correlated with pathologic complete response, and we found that GREB1 expression was more effectively reduced with letrozole versus tamoxifen. The hormone receptors ESR1 and PGR1 were among the genes most closely co-regulated with GREB1 at the transcriptome level across human tissues, and depletion of GREB1 silenced ESR1 expression, supporting a direct functional role for GREB1 in estrogen receptor signal

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transduction. Letrozole and tamoxifen are described to possess distinct clinical responses reflected in reduced metastasis at distant sites (1). We are currently studying GREB1 to define its function in estrogen signaling.

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References

1. Breast International Group (BIG) 1-98 Collaborative Group, 2005. A comparison of letrozole and tamoxifen in postmenopausal women with early breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(26), pp.2747-2757.
2. Gao, H.F., Lin, Y.Y., Zhu, T., Ji, F., Zhang, L.L., Yang, C.Q., Yang, M., Li, J.Q., Cheng, M.Y. and Wang, K., 2021. Adjuvant CDK4/6 inhibitors combined with endocrine therapy in HR-positive, HER2-negative early breast cancer: A meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *The Breast*, 59, pp.165-175.

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Methods

We performed an expression screen for genes that mediate resistance in breast cancers that are hormone receptor positive, measuring total transcription in cells that had been *in vitro* selected to develop resistance to endocrine therapy, in the primary tumors of humans with hormone receptor positive (luminal A and luminal B breast cancer), and studied the biologic functions, translational and clinical relevance of the identified gene product GREB1 using R-based computational methods and the following datasets, in addition to the aforementioned: GSE241654, GSE241942, GSE125738, GSE59515, GSE104050, GSE165571, GSE159968, GSE77948, GSE43809, GSE221439, GSE80077 and GSE132055. We used SEEK for computational transcriptional co-regulation studies.